

TropRice: a decision support system for irrigated rice

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TropRice is a knowledge-driven support system that delivers expert information to help technology transfer agents make more informed practical decisions related to rice production in the tropics. TropRice was developed in response to the recognition that many researchers, field extension agents, and farmers do not have access to the most up-to-date information on how to improve their rice-growing practices. Computers, the Internet, and information technologies offer innovative ways to package and present practical information.

Target audience and environment

TropRice is primarily aimed at intermediary technology transfer agents—the people who work with farmers in the field and need practical information on production and postproduction practices. They can be in government, non-government extension organizations, or the private sector. In addition, researchers will find TropRice useful as both a training and field practice resource.

Although TropRice is aimed at irrigated tropical rice, it is *not* a single sys-

tem for all irrigated tropical rice systems. Although some information is generic, other information is site- or region-specific. TropRice is in fact a template (i.e., prototype) that is intended for modification by IRRI's collaborators to suit their particular rice-growing environments. The present system is aimed at irrigated rice in a lowland production environment. However, as additional information on improved practices for various environments and/or modules within TropRice becomes available, it will enter or be linked to the system.

Content

TropRice aims to provide practical information on all aspects of production and postproduction management of rice and answers questions related to

- Management timetable
- Land preparation and leveling
- Rice varieties
- Crop establishment
- Water management
- Nutrient management
- Pest management
 - weed management
 - insect management
 - disease management
 - snails, rats, and birds
 - safe applications

- Postproduction
- Economics

In addition, TropRice contains two slide shows—one titled "Technology changes in Asia: The changing face of Asian rice production" and the other one on "Seed quality."

TropRice is now being used in China, India, Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam and is being translated or localized by national collaborators for local conditions in these same countries. Some of these collaborators also evaluate TropRice content for accuracy, reliability, depth, and breadth and recommend changes.

Graphical user interface and technology requirements

TropRice screens are designed to facilitate navigation. The user interface for TropRice is set up to maximize usability through a navigation scheme built upon the standard Microsoft Windows Help function, an index, a search feature, and a glossary.

The content is structured as information rather than education, as the intent of TropRice is to provide reference rather than on-line instruction. When appropriate, information is complemented by graphics, diagrams, and Java-enabled calculators.

TropRice is written with open-source development software that will output to print, compiled help, or html. The primary delivery method will be on-line and, for those without on-line access, CD-ROM. An Internet browser such as Microsoft Internet Explorer (version 4.0, or later) is required for access. Hardware requirements are based on the ability to run the required software. At the minimum, your computer needs to be

- Windows 95/98/NT-based
- Multimedia capable with a minimum of 16-Mb RAM, 66-mHz processor, and 100-Mb hard disk.

